

Phenotypic and genotypic comparison of biofilm producers among carbapenem susceptible and resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: About one third of all Gram-negative bacterial infections globally are caused by *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. These bacteria readily become drug resistant and form biofilms that significantly complicates treatment of infections.

OBJECTIVE: This study aimed to compare biofilm production in carbapenem-resistant (CR) and carbapenem-susceptible (CS) *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains and to evaluate the association between biofilm production, carbapenem resistance and the presence of virulence genes *mrkA*, *wbbM*, *wzm*, *luxS* implicated in biofilm formation.

METHODS: A total of 37 CR and 63 CS *K. pneumoniae* isolates were included in the study. Antibiotic susceptibility testing was performed using an automated Vitek 2 system. The presence of virulence genes (*mrkA*, *wbbM*, *wzm*, *luxS*) was investigated by PCR. Biofilm formation was assessed using the spectrophotometric microplate method.

RESULTS: Overall, 65% of isolates were multidrug-resistant (MDR). The carbapenem resistance rate was 37%. CR strains showed significantly higher resistance to multiple antibiotics compared with CS strains. Biofilm production was detected in 76% of all isolates: 100% of CR strains and 61.9% of CS strains. The most frequently detected gene was *mrkA* (73%), followed by *wbbM* (57%), *luxS* (52%), and *wzm* (32%).

CONCLUSION: MDR rates were higher in CR strains and in isolates with biofilm production. MIC values for ertapenem, meropenem, amikacin, piperacillin-tazobactam, cefoxitin, ceftazidime, and ceftriaxone were higher in biofilm-producing strains. Biofilm production was statistically significantly associated with MDR and strongly associated with carbapenem resistance, whereas the presence of individual virulence genes did not show any statistically significant association with it.

Keywords: *K. pneumoniae*, carbapenem, resistance, biofilm

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INTRODUCTION

Klebsiella pneumoniae is a Gram-negative bacterium that can persist in healthy individuals without causing infection, primarily colonizing the gastrointestinal tract, respiratory system, and skin [1]. It is an opportunistic pathogen that commonly causes severe infections in immunocompromised individuals, such as elderly patients, newborns, and those with diabetes, malignancy, or chronic alcoholism [1, 2]. *K. pneumoniae* is also a leading cause of bacterial pneumonia, meningitis, and liver abscesses [2]. Importantly, it spreads rapidly in healthcare settings and is a major cause of nosocomial infections [3].

The pathogenicity of *K. pneumoniae* is mediated by multiple virulence factors [2], including capsules, lipopolysaccharides (LPS), siderophores, and fimbriae [4]. These virulence factors contribute to the ability of bacterial growth, colonization, infection of the host organism, and resistance to the host defenses [2]. Another key factor is its ability to form biofilms on the surface of medical devices such as catheters and ventilators [5]. Biofilms are complex structures of polysaccharides, proteins, and extracellular DNA [5] that confer protection of bacteria against antibiotics and host defenses. Biofilm-associated bacteria are highly resistant to antimicrobial therapy, making infections difficult to eradicate. It was shown that biofilm-producing *K. pneumoniae* develop resistance after long-term treatment with antibiotics such as ampicillin and ciprofloxacin [6]. It is also assumed that biofilm can protect bacteria against host defense mechanisms [7].

Antibiotic resistance in *K. pneumoniae* became a major problem since it makes difficult to treat even simple infections caused by these bacteria in patients [2]. With rising resistance to penicillins and cephalosporins, carbapenems such as imipenem and meropenem have been widely used for treatment infections caused by *K. pneumoniae* [8]. However, increased use of carbapenems against bacteria producing expanded-spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBL) has led to the emergence of carbapenem-resistant (CR) and multidrug-resistant (MDR) strains [8]. These strains pose a significant challenge in clinical management due to limited therapeutic options.

We investigated biofilm production by CR and carbapenem-susceptible (CS) *K. pneumoniae* strains isolated from various clinical samples at the Microbiology Laboratory of Hatay Mustafa Kemal University Hospital. Our study aimed to explore the association between the presence of the certain virulence genes in *K. pneumoniae* strains, biofilm formation in these strains, and their

resistance to carbapenems. This goal was achieved by detection of the selected virulence genes implicated in biofilm formation (*mrkA*, *wbbM*, *wzm*, *luxS*) in both CR and CS strains of bacteria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ethical approval

The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Hatay Mustafa Kemal University (decision No. 08, 26/08/2021).

Bacterial strains

Between February 2021 and January 2022, 37 CR and 63 CS *K. pneumoniae* isolates were recovered from clinical samples (urine, wound, sputum, tracheal aspirate, blood) processed at the Microbiology Laboratory of Bacteriology Department of Hatay Mustafa Kemal University Hospital.

Isolation, identification, and antimicrobial susceptibility testing

Specimens were cultured on eosin methylene blue (EMB) agar (Merck, Germany) and blood agar (Merck, Germany) and incubated at 37°C for 24 h. Identification of *K. pneumoniae* was carried out using Gram staining and conventional biochemical tests, including oxidase, triple sugar iron agar, IMViC (indole, methyl red, Voges-Proskauer, citrate), and urease tests, and was confirmed using the VITEK 2 automated system (bioMérieux, France). Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was also performed with the Vitek 2 system and interpreted according to European Committee for Antibiotic Sensitivity Testing (EUCAST) guidelines [9]. Isolates resistant to ertapenem, meropenem, or imipenem were classified as CR. Multidrug resistance was defined as resistance to at least one agent in three or more antimicrobial classes [10].

Biofilm production assay

Biofilm formation was assessed using the spectrophotometric microplate method (Thermo Fisher Scientific Oy, Finland) [11]. Bacterial strains grown on EMB agar (Merck, Germany) were inoculated in 10 ml of tryptic soy broth (TSB, Merck, Germany) and incubated at 37°C for 24 h, adjusted to 0.5 McFarland standard ($\sim 1 \times 10^8$ CFU/mL) with physiological salt water (PSW), and inoculated into 96-well microplates. Subsequently, an additional 200 μ L of TSB was added to each well and the microplate was incubated at 37°C for 24 h. The supernatant was separated, and the residue was washed three times with PSW and left drying on the air.

Then 200 µL of the crystal violet solution was added to each well and microplate was left for 20 min at room temperature. The wells were washed three times with PSW, allowed to dry and the residue was dissolved in DMSO. Optical density (OD) of DMSO solution at 492 nm was measured using spectroscopic photometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific Oy, Finland). All the measurements were performed in triplicates. Biofilm formation was classified as negative, weak, moderate, or strong according to OD cut-off values (Table 1) [11]. *K. pneumoniae* ATCC 700603 was used as a positive control, and *E. coli* ATCC 25922 as a negative control.

Table 1. Evaluation of the degrees of biofilm production [11]

OD ^a ≤OD ^c	Negative
OD ^c <OD≤(2xOD ^c)	Weak
(2xOD ^c)<OD≤(4xOD ^c)	Middle
(4xOD ^c)<OD	Strong

OD^a – Optical Density, OD^c – negative control

Detection of virulence genes in *K. pneumoniae* using PCR

Bacterial DNA was extracted using a commercial Bacteria Genomic DNA Isolation Kit (HibriGen, Turkey) according to manufacturer's instructions. PCR amplification was performed for *mrkA*, *wbbM*, *wzm*, and *luxS* genes according to method described by Vuotto et al. [12]. The corresponding primers for *mrkA*, *wbbM*, *wzm*, *luxS* genes are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Primer Sequences for *mrkA*, *wbbM*, *wzm*, *luxS* genes

Gene	Primer sequence	Product size (bp)
<i>mrkA</i> -F	5'-ACGTCTCTAACTGCCAGGC-3'	115
<i>mrkA</i> -R	5'-TAGCCCTGTTGTTTGCTGGT-3'	
<i>wbbM</i> -F	5'-ATGCGGGTGAGAACAAACCA-3'	122
<i>wbbM</i> -R	5'-AGCCGCTAACGACATCTGAC-3'	
<i>wzm</i> -F	5'-TGCCAGTTTCGGCCACTAAC-3'	148
<i>wzm</i> -R	5'-GACAACAATAACCGGGATGG-3'	
<i>luxS</i> -F	5'-AGTGATGCCGGAACGCGG-3'	148
<i>luxS</i> -R	5'-CGGTGTACCAATCAGGCTC-3'	

Amplification conditions included an initial denaturation at 94°C for 5 min, followed by 30 cycles of 94°C for 30 s, 58°C for 30 s, and 72°C for 30 s, with a final extension at 72°C for 10 min. PCR products in 0.5X TBE buffer (Thermo Scientific, Lithuania) together with a DNA marker (100-1500 bp) (abm, Canada) were loaded on 2% agarose gel and separated by electrophoresis (Wealtec, Elite 300 Plus, Taiwan) at 100 V during 50 min. The separated products were visualized under UV light (Wealtec Dolphin-View, USA).

Statistical analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0 (IBM, USA). Categorical variables were compared using the chi-square test, and continuous variables with the Mann-Whitney U test. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant. The relationships between the presence of virulence genes, carbapenem resistance, biofilm production, and multidrug (MDR) resistance was examined using logistic regression analysis.

RESULTS

A total of 100 *K. pneumoniae* isolates were analyzed: 37 CR and 63 CS strains. Thirty percent of samples were obtained from ICUs, 31% from outpatients, and 39% from other hospitalized patients. Most strains were isolated from urine (62%), followed by tracheal aspirates (13%), wounds (12%), blood (11%), and sputum (2%). The distribution of isolates by clinical source and carbapenem susceptibility is summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Clinical sources of *K. pneumoniae* isolates and their carbapenem susceptibility

Sample	Carbapenem-susceptible n (%)	Carbapenem-resistant n (%)	Total n (%)
Blood	3 (27.3)	8 (72.7)	11 (11)
Urine	48 (77.4)	14 (22.6)	62 (62)
Sputum	1 (50.0)	1 (50.0)	2 (2)
Tracheal aspirate	5 (38.5)	8 (61.5)	13 (13)
Wound	6 (50.0)	6 (50.0)	12 (12)
Total	63 (63.0)	37 (37.0)	100

Carbapenem resistance was detected in 37% of isolates. Resistance was significantly higher among blood isolates (72.7%) compared with urine (22.6%) (p=0.003). Equal rates of susceptibility and resistance were observed in sputum and wound isolates. More than half of the isolates from ICUs (53.4%) were CR, whereas isolates from other wards showed a resistance rate of 30%. No statistically significant correlation was found between carbapenem resistance and hospital ward of origin (p=0.070).

CR strains were resistant to ampicillin (100%), amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (AMC, 100%), cefuroxime (100%), piperacillin-tazobactam (PTZ, 100%), ceftazidime (97.3%), ceftazidime (97.3%), cefuroxime axetil (97.3%), and ciprofloxacin (91.9%). In contrast, CS strains showed resistance mainly to ampicillin (100%), cefuroxime (53.9%), cefuroxime axetil (52.4%), AMC (47.6%), and ceftriaxone (47.6%).

Overall, CR strains exhibited significantly higher resistance to multiple antibiotics including AMC, PTZ, cefoxitin, ceftazidime, ceftriaxone, cefuroxime, cefuroxime axetil, amikacin, ciprofloxacin, and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (SXT) compared with CS strains ($p < 0.001$). All isolates were resistant to ampicillin. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values were higher in CR strains than in CS strains, except for gentamicin, for which MICs were similar in both groups.

The overall resistance rates were as follows: ampicillin (100%), cefuroxime (71%), cefuroxime axetil (69%), AMC (67%), ceftriaxone (67%), ceftazidime (65%), ciprofloxacin (53%), PTZ (50%), SXT (46%), cefoxitin (42%), cefixime (38%), ertapenem (37%), gentamicin (24%), meropenem (22%), and amikacin (22%).

One *K. pneumoniae* strain (1%) produced a strong biofilm, 30 strains (30%) produced a medium biofilm, and 45 strains (45%) produced a weak biofilm, while the remaining 24 strains (24%) did not produce any biofilm (Table 4). In total, 76% of the studied isolates were biofilm producers. The only strain that produced a strong biofilm was resistant to carbapenems. Medium biofilm production was more frequent among CR strains (56.8%) than CS strains (14.3%). Weak biofilm production was observed in 47.6% of CS strains and in 40.5% of CR strains. All CR strains exhibited some level of biofilm production

(strong, medium, or weak), whereas 38.1% of CS strains did not produce a biofilm ($p < 0.001$). The relationship between biofilm production and carbapenem resistance is shown in Table 4 and Fig. 1.

There was no statistically significant association between the source of clinical samples and biofilm production ($p = 0.103$).

The presence of *mrkA*, *wbbM*, *wzm*, *luxS* genes was evaluated by means of electrophoresis of the PCR products (Fig. 2).

Biofilm formation was detected in 57 of 73 (78.1%) *mrkA*-positive strains, 43 of 57 (75.4%) *wbbM*-positive strains, 25 of 32 (78.1%) *wzm*-positive strains, and 39 of 52 (75%) *luxS*-positive strains. These results are summarized in Table 5, Fig. 3.

No statistically significant correlation was observed between genes presence and biofilm production ($p > 0.05$), as a high rate of biofilm formation was also observed in strains lacking these genes. Likewise, the presence of these genes did not significantly affect carbapenem susceptibility ($p > 0.05$, Table 6, Fig. 4).

Overall, 65 strains (65%) were MDR, including 63.3% of isolates from intensive care patients and 65.7% from other clinics. MDR rates were significantly higher among CR strains ($p < 0.001$): all CR strains were MDR, whereas only 44.4% of CS strains were MDR. Among the 76 biofilm-producing strains, 54 (71.1%) were MDR and 22 (28.9%)

Table 4. Relationship between biofilm production and carbapenem resistance in *K. pneumoniae* strains

Biofilm	Carbapenem-susceptible n (%)	Carbapenem-resistant n (%)	Total n (%)	p-value
Strong	0 (0)	1 (2.7)	1 (1)	<0.001
Medium	9 (14.3)	21 (56.8)	30 (30)	
Weak	30 (47.6)	15 (40.5)	45 (45)	
No biofilm	24 (38.1)	0 (0)	24 (24)	
Total	63 (100)	37 (100)	100 (100)	

Fig. 1. Correlation between biofilm-forming ability and carbapenem resistance in *K. pneumoniae* strains.

Fig. 2. The images of *mrkA*, *wbbM*, *luxS*, and *wzm* genes in agarose gel electrophoresis.

Table 5. Correlation of biofilm production with the presence of *mrkA*, *wbbM*, *wzm*, and *luxS* genes in *K. pneumoniae* strains

Gene	Biofilm Producers n (%)	Non-producers n (%)	Total n (%)	p-value
<i>mrkA</i>	Present: 57 (78.1)	16 (21.9)	73 (100)	0.423
	Absent: 19 (70.4)	8 (29.6)	27 (100)	
<i>wbbM</i>	Present: 43 (75.4)	14 (24.6)	57 (100)	0.880
	Absent: 33 (76.7)	10 (23.3)	43 (100)	
<i>wzm</i>	Present: 25 (78.1)	7 (21.9)	32 (100)	0.733
	Absent: 51 (75.0)	17 (25.0)	68 (100)	
<i>luxS</i>	Present: 39 (75.0)	13 (25.0)	52 (100)	0.807
	Absent: 37 (77.1)	11 (22.9)	48 (100)	

Fig. 3. Correlation between biofilm-forming ability and the presence of *mrkA*, *wbbM*, *wzm*, and *luxS* genes in *K. pneumoniae* strains.

were non-MDR. Among the 24 non-biofilm-producing strains, 11 (45.8%) were MDR and 13 (54.2%) were non-MDR. The proportion of MDR isolates was statistically significantly higher among biofilm producers than non-producers (p=0.024).

The data on the virulence genes presence, drug resistance, and biofilm production in different bacterial strains are shown in Table 7, Fig. 5, 6.

Among the studied isolates, 73 (73%) carried the *mrkA* gene, 57 (57%) carried *wbbM*, 52 (52%) carried *luxS*, and 32 (32%) carried *wzm* gene. Co-occurrence of multiple genes was observed in several isolates: all four genes (*mrkA*, *wbbM*, *wzm*, *luxS*) in 13 strains; *mrkA*, *wbbM*, and *luxS* in 18; *mrkA*, *wbbM*, and *wzm* in 9; *wbbM*, *wzm*, and *luxS* in 3; and *mrkA*, *wzm*, and *luxS* in 3 strains. Pairs of genes were also detected: *mrkA* + *wzm* in 2 strains, *mrkA* + *wbbM* in 8, *wbbM* + *luxS* in 2, and *mrkA* + *luxS* in 6. Genes detected individually included *mrkA* (14 strains), *luxS* (7 strains), *wbbM* (4 strains), and *wzm* (2 strain). Nine strains did not carry any of the studied genes.

Biofilm-producing strains also showed higher resistance to piperacillin-tazobactam (PTZ, p=0.006), ceftazidime (p=0.009), ceftaxime (p=0.001), ceftriaxone (p=0.042), meropenem (p=0.002), ertapenem (p<0.01), and amikacin (p=0.02). No statistically significant associations were found between biofilm production and resistance to AMC (p=0.426), cefixime (p=0.780), cefuroxime (p=0.117), cefuroxime axetil (p=0.164), gentamicin (p=1.0), ciprofloxacin (p<0.052), or SXT (p=0.153).

Logistic regression analysis was performed to evaluate the relationships between the presence of virulence genes, carbapenem resistance, biofilm production, and multidrug resistance. We found a statistically significant correlation between multidrug resistance and biofilm production in the studied *K. pneumoniae* strains (p=0.024). However, no statistically significant associations were observed between other variables (p>0.05 in all models).

Table 6. Correlation of carbapenem susceptibility with the presence of *mrkA*, *wbbM*, *wzm*, and *luxS* genes in *K. pneumoniae* strains

Gene	Carbapenem-susceptible n (%)	Carbapenem-resistant n (%)	Total n (%)	p-value
<i>mrkA</i>	Present: 47 (64.4)	26 (35.6)	73 (100)	0.637
	Absent: 16 (59.3)	11 (40.7)	27 (100)	
<i>wbbM</i>	Present: 37 (64.9)	20 (35.1)	57 (100)	0.648
	Absent: 26 (60.5)	17 (39.5)	43 (100)	
<i>wzm</i>	Present: 24 (75.0)	8 (25.0)	32 (100)	0.088
	Absent: 39 (57.4)	29 (42.6)	68 (100)	
<i>luxS</i>	Present: 33 (63.5)	19 (36.5)	52 (100)	0.921
	Absent: 30 (62.5)	18 (37.5)	48 (100)	

Fig. 4. Relationship between carbapenem resistance and the presence of *mrkA*, *wbbM*, *wzm*, and *luxS* genes in *K. pneumoniae* strains.

Table 7. Virulence genes presence, drug resistance, and biofilm production in bacterial strains

Number of strains	Virulent genes present	Drug resistance				Biofilm produced			
		CS ^a	CR ^b	MDR ^c	Strong biofilm	Medium biofilm	Weak biofilm	No biofilm	
		N	N	N	N	N	N	N	
13	<i>mrkA</i> , <i>wbbM</i> , <i>wzm</i> , and <i>luxS</i>	9	4	8	0	3	7	3	
18	<i>mrkA</i> , <i>wbbM</i> , and <i>luxS</i>	10	8	12	1	6	8	3	
9	<i>mrkA</i> , <i>wbbM</i> , and <i>wzm</i>	7	2	6	0	2	6	1	
3	<i>wbbM</i> , <i>wzm</i> , and <i>luxS</i>	2	1	2	0	1	1	1	
3	<i>mrkA</i> , <i>wzm</i> , and <i>luxS</i>	2	1	2	0	0	2	1	
2	<i>mrkA</i> and <i>wzm</i>	2	0	1	0	0	2	0	
8	<i>mrkA</i> and <i>wbbM</i>	6	2	5	0	1	4	3	
2	<i>wbbM</i> and <i>luxS</i>	1	1	2	0	1	1	0	
6	<i>mrkA</i> and <i>luxS</i>	4	2	5	0	2	3	1	
14	<i>mrkA</i>	7	7	11	0	8	3	3	
4	<i>wbbM</i>	2	2	3	0	1	1	2	
2	<i>wzm</i>	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	
7	<i>luxS</i>	5	2	3	0	2	2	3	
9	No genes	4	5	5	0	3	5	1	
100	Total	63	37	65	1	30	45	24	

CS^a – carbapenem susceptible, CR^b – carbapenem resistant, MDR^c – multidrug resistant

Fig. 5. Antimicrobial resistance of *K. pneumoniae* strains containing different virulence genes. CS – carbapenem susceptible, CR – carbapenem resistant, MDR – multidrug resistant.

Fig. 6. Biofilm production by *K. pneumoniae* strains containing different virulence genes.

DISCUSSION

K. pneumoniae is a major cause of nosocomial infections in ICU patients, primarily affecting the respiratory tract, urinary tract, and bloodstream [13]. Ballen et al. [14] reported that, among the isolates they collected between 2016 and 2017, 57 (44.9%) originated from urine, 37 (29.1%) from respiratory samples (sputum and tracheal aspirates), and 33 (26%) from blood, in their investigation of *K. pneumoniae* antibiotic resistance and virulence profiles. In another study conducted in Tehran between January 2018 and July 2019, Mirzaie and Ranjbarik [15] found that *K. pneumoniae* strains were most frequently isolated from urine (70%), followed by blood (20%), sputum (6%), and bronchoalveolar lavage samples (4%).

In our study, *K. pneumoniae* was isolated most frequently from urine (62%), followed by tracheal aspirates (13%), wound samples (12%), blood (11%), and sputum (2%). Similar to other reports, urine was the most common source of *K. pneumoniae* isolates, with additional sources including blood, wounds, and respiratory samples.

Studies from other countries have also demonstrated high isolation rates of *K. pneumoniae* from ICU patients. For example, Shadkam et al. [16] reported that, of

100 isolates collected in Iran between April 2016 and January 2017, 36% were from ICU patients and 64% from other wards. Similarly, Sanikhani et al. [17] found that, among 102 isolates, 51% originated from the ICU, 12.7% from surgical units, and 10.8% and 8.8% from emergency departments. In Portugal, Aires-de-Sousa et al. [18] reported that 15.2% of 46 *K. pneumoniae* isolates associated with carbapenemase production were collected from ICU patients.

In our study, 30% (n=30) of isolates were obtained from ICU patients, while the remaining 70% were from other hospital wards. These findings indicate that a substantial proportion of *K. pneumoniae* isolates are derived from ICU patients. This is consistent with the increased risk of infection among ICU patients due to impaired host defenses and prolonged exposure to invasive procedures [19].

Commonly used antibiotics for the treatment of Gram-negative bacterial infections include cephalosporins, penicillins, aminoglycosides, fluoroquinolones, and carbapenems. However, the widespread presence of resistance mechanisms due to bacterial synthesis of β -lactamases, cephalosporinases, and carbapenemases complicates therapy and limits treatment options [20].

In Montenegro, Mijović et al. [21] reported the highest resistance rate to ceftriaxone (93.6%) among 78 *K. pneumoniae* isolates collected in hospitals between 2016 and 2018. Resistance was also high to ceftazidime (90.8%), gentamicin (89.9%), and AMC (87%), while carbapenem resistance was relatively low (7.69%). Similarly, Alcántar-Curiel et al. [22] analyzed 168 *K. pneumoniae* strains isolated over a 45-month period (February 1999 – October 2002) in Hospital Civil de Guadalajara, Mexico, and found resistance rates of 100% to ampicillin, 97% to cefuroxime, 81.5% to gentamicin, 72% to ceftazidime, 68.5% to ceftriaxone, and 67.2% to amikacin. In Beijing, China, Li et al. [23] observed that nearly all *K. pneumoniae* isolates (99.6%) were resistant to ampicillin, with additional high resistance rates to SXT (52.9%), ceftriaxone (49.3%), and ceftazidime (49.3%). In contrast, carbapenem resistance was lower, with 7.2% and 5.8% resistance to ertapenem and imipenem, respectively.

In our study, the highest resistance rates were observed for ampicillin (100%), followed by cefuroxime (71%), cefuroxime axetil (69%), ceftriaxone (67%), ceftazidime (65%), and AMC (67%). Resistance to fluoroquinolones and β -lactam/ β -lactamase inhibitor combinations was also common, with ciprofloxacin (53%), PTZ (50%), and SXT (46%). Lower resistance rates were found for ceftazidime (42%), cefixime (38%), ertapenem (37%), gentamicin (24%), meropenem (22%), and amikacin (22%). These results are consistent with previous studies, which also identified ampicillin, cephalosporins, and aminoglycosides as antibiotics with the highest resistance rates in *K. pneumoniae*. Notably, *K. pneumoniae* is intrinsically resistant to ampicillin [9], explaining the uniform 100% resistance observed.

Enterobacteriales in general have acquired resistance to multiple antibiotic classes, leading to the increased use of carbapenems. However, the rapid spread of carbapenemase genes in bacteria has resulted in a concerning rise in carbapenem resistance [24]. According to the U.S. “Antibiotic Resistance Threats 2019” report, carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriales (CRE) caused 11,400 infections among hospitalized patients in 2014, 11,500 in 2015, and 13,100 in both 2016 and 2017, with approximately 1,100 deaths annually [25]. The increase in CRE cases has been strongly linked to plasmid-mediated carbapenem resistance [26]. Both the United States and China have reported a marked rise in CR *K. pneumoniae* isolates over recent years [26, 27].

According to the “Central Asian and European Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance 2020” report, carbapenem resistance in *K. pneumoniae* strains isolated in Turkey was 39% [28]. In isolates obtained from

blood and cerebrospinal fluid, resistance rates were particularly high: AMC (75%), cefotaxime/ceftriaxone (73%), ceftazidime (70%), gentamicin/tobramycin (65%), PTZ (60%), imipenem/meropenem (39%), and amikacin (27%) [28].

The 2020 report [28] indicated that MDR rates in *K. pneumoniae* isolates from Turkey were approximately 40%, with resistance to third-generation cephalosporins exceeding 50%. Hu et al. [27], in a retrospective study from Zhejiang Province, China (2008–2019), documented an increase in carbapenem resistance from 2.5% to 15.8%. Similarly, Indrajith et al. [29] reported high resistance among 89 MDR *K. pneumoniae* isolates: 38% to imipenem, 31% to meropenem, and 52% to ertapenem. Shao et al. [30] studied elderly patients with lower respiratory tract infections in China and found that 31 of 258 *K. pneumoniae* strains (12.0%) were CR. In our study, 37 (37%) of 100 *K. pneumoniae* isolates were CR, with resistance rates of 22% to ertapenem and 37% to meropenem.

MDR *K. pneumoniae* poses a serious clinical challenge due to limited treatment options, prolonged hospitalizations, and increased healthcare costs [31]. Internationally, Khairy et al. [32] reported an MDR prevalence of 16.8% (42/250 isolates) in Egypt, while Farhadi et al. [33] found 58% MDR among 100 isolates from hospitals in northern Iran. In our study, the MDR prevalence was 65%, with similar rates in ICU (63.3%) and non-ICU (65.7%) isolates, that included 28 (44.4%) of CS and 37 of CR strains. No statistically significant difference in MDR prevalence was found between ICU and other wards ($p=0.0819$). Importantly, all CR strains were also MDR.

Biofilm formation provides *K. pneumoniae* with protection against a wide range of adverse environmental conditions, including ultraviolet radiation, extreme temperatures, high pH, high salt concentrations, high pressure, nutrient limitation, and exposure to antibiotics [34, 35]. The capacity for biofilm formation significantly enhances bacterial defense mechanisms and contributes to increased antimicrobial resistance [34, 35]. Studies of biofilm-producing microorganisms have shown that bacteria located near the biofilm surface grow more rapidly and display greater resistance to external agents compared to those embedded in deeper layers of the biofilm [36].

Several studies have reported a strong association between biofilm formation and antibiotic resistance in *K. pneumoniae*. Rahdar et al. [37] examined 160 isolates collected from military hospitals between April 2018 and March 2019 and found that among 92 CS strains, 33.6% were strong, 50% moderate, and 16.3% weak biofilm

producers. In contrast, 68 CR strains showed markedly higher biofilm-forming ability, with 77.9% classified as strong and 22% as moderate producers. Consistent with these findings, our study demonstrated biofilm production in 61.9% of CS strains, whereas all CR strains (100%) produced biofilms. Although we observed a significant correlation between carbapenem resistance and biofilm production, our study was focused on detection of the selected virulence genes implicated in biofilm formation (*mrkA*, *wbbM*, *wzm*, *luxS*) in the *K pneumoniae* isolates. However, it's important to remember that carbapenem resistance in these bacteria is primarily mediated by carbapenemase genes such as *blaKPC*, *blaNDM*, *blaVIM*, and *blaOXA*, which encode enzymes that directly degrade carbapenems.

Similarly, Di Domenico et al. [38] reported that, among 86 CR *K. pneumoniae* isolates from oncology patients, 48 (55.8%) were strong biofilm producers and 38 (44.2%) were weak producers. Haghififar et al. [39] analyzed 128 isolates and identified 57 as MDR. Of these MDR isolates, 37 (65%) produced weak, 12 (21%) moderate, and 8 (14%) strong biofilms. In our study, among the 65 MDR strains, 54 (83%) exhibited biofilm production, while 11 (17%) did not ($p=0.024$).

The virulence factors of *K. pneumoniae*, including the capsule, lipopolysaccharides (LPS), siderophores, and pili, enhance pathogenicity by increasing the bacterium's ability to cause disease and resist environmental stress [40]. Several virulence-associated genes are also involved in biofilm formation. For example, the *mrk* genes encode type 3 fimbriae that mediate adhesion [41], while *wbbM* and *wzm* encode enzymes of the *wb* gene cluster involved in LPS synthesis [42, 43]. In addition, the *luxS* gene has an autoinducer and regulatory role in quorum sensing, thereby contributing to biofilm development [45, 46].

We examined the presence of *mrkA*, *wbbM*, *wzm*, and *luxS* genes in bacterial isolates, which are believed to play a role in biofilm production and evaluated their association with biofilm formation. Among the 100 *K. pneumoniae* strains analyzed by PCR, the most frequently detected gene was *mrkA* (73%), followed by *wbbM* (57%), *luxS* (52%), and *wzm* (32%). Of the 73 *mrkA*-positive isolates, 57 (78.1%) produced biofilms, while 16 (21.9%) did not. Similarly, biofilm production was detected in 43 (75.4%) of 57 *wbbM*-positive strains, 25 (78.1%) of 32 *wzm*-positive strains, and 39 (75.0%) of 52 *luxS*-positive strains. Although biofilm production was more common among isolates that contained these genes, these differences were not statistically significant, as biofilm formation was also frequent in the strains that did not contain them. It should be noted that *mrkA* and *luxS* genes are highly conserved, whereas *wbbM* and *wzm*

can vary between strains since they encode different surface polysaccharides. This variability may help explain differences in gene prevalence across isolates.

Our findings are broadly consistent with previous reports. Mirzaie and Ranjbar [15] found that 92% of their *K. pneumoniae* isolates from Tehran (2018–2019) were MDR and 48% were resistant to imipenem. In their biofilm assays, 77% of isolates produced biofilm, compared to 76% in our study. They also reported that 89% of biofilm producers had an MDR phenotype, indicating a significant association between biofilm formation and MDR. In our data, 65% of strains were MDR, and 83% of MDR isolates produced biofilm ($p=0.024$).

Regarding specific genes, Mirzaie and Ranjbar [15] reported *mrkA* in 88% of isolates, compared to 73% in our study. They found that all biofilm producers carried *mrkA*, whereas we observed *mrkA* in 57 (75%) of the 76 biofilm-forming isolates. The higher prevalence in their study may be explained by the predominance of MDR strains in their cohort. The *mrkA* gene contributes to adhesion to epithelial and endothelial cells in the urinary tract and may play a role in biofilm formation [46]. Vuotto et al. [12] also highlighted the importance of *mrkA*, reporting that all the MDR strains produced biofilms, while 67.5% of them produced strong biofilms, and that *mrkA* facilitated biofilm adherence. In our study, 78.1% of *mrkA*-positive isolates produced biofilms, and *mrkA* was especially common among MDR strains (76.9%), followed by *wbbM* (58.5%), *luxS* (52.3%), and *wzm* (29.2%). Among CR isolates, *mrkA* was detected in 70.3%, *wbbM* in 54.1%, *luxS* in 51.4%, and *wzm* in 21.6%. Even when *mrkA* is absent or downregulated, bacteria may still form biofilms through other mechanisms. For instance, strains may carry the *fim* gene cluster encoding type 1 fimbriae, which can also contribute to adhesion and biofilm formation. Thus, biofilm formation in strains lacking *mrkA*, *wbbM*, or *wzm* suggests that other virulence factors can compensate for their absence [47, 48].

Despite the high prevalence of these genes, our analysis showed no statistically significant association between *mrkA*, *wbbM*, *wzm*, or *luxS* and either biofilm production or carbapenem susceptibility ($p>0.05$ in all models). The latter result could be explained by the low number of carbapenem-resistant strains analyzed in our study. Production of biofilms was common even among strains that did not carry these genes, suggesting that biofilm formation is influenced by multiple factors beyond the presence of these virulence genes. It is important to note that these genes must be actively expressed. If downregulated, they cannot produce the corresponding proteins and therefore will have no influence on the process of biofilm formation [48–50].

On the other hand, statistically significant correlation was observed between biofilm formation and antibiotic resistance. Thus, the MDR rate was significantly higher in CR strains compared to CS strains ($p < 0.001$), and MDR was more prevalent among biofilm producers ($p = 0.024$). Biofilm-producing isolates showed significantly higher resistance to PTZ ($p = 0.006$), ceftazidime ($p = 0.009$), cefoxitin ($p = 0.001$), ceftriaxone ($p = 0.042$), meropenem ($p = 0.002$), ertapenem ($p < 0.01$), and amikacin ($p = 0.02$). Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values for these antibiotics were also higher in biofilm producers ($p < 0.05$).

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CONCLUSION

In our study, the rate of carbapenem resistance was higher in *K. pneumoniae* strains isolated from patients in ICUs compared to those from other hospital wards. Overall, our findings indicate that although the *mrkA*, *wbbM*, *wzm*, and *luxS* genes are frequently detected in *K. pneumoniae* isolates, their presence alone does not reliably predict biofilm formation or carbapenem resistance. In contrast, we observed a strong association between biofilm formation and antibiotic resistance: all CR strains, which were also MDR, produced biofilms, whereas only 44.4% of CS strains were MDR and 61.9% of CS strains produced biofilms.

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